

Studies in Furan Derivatives. Part VII*. Synthesis of 4-methylfuro (5,4':6,7)coumarin and Attempted Synthesis of Furo (5,4':6,7) coumarin

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7-Formyl-4-methylcoumarin, prepared from 7-bromomethyl-4-methyl coumarin, on Elbs-persulphate oxidation gave 6-hydroxy-7-formyl-4-methyl coumarin. On condensation with ethyl bromoacetate it gave the 6-carbethoxy derivative. The acid obtained on hydrolysis of this was cyclised and decarboxylated to get the title compound. Synthesis of furo(5,4':6,7)coumarin from 6-hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin by a similar process did not succeed. The intermediate 6-carbethoxy derivative on hydrolysis gave a polymeric product. Condensation of 6-hydroxy-7-formyl coumarin with ethyl bromomalonate gave 2'-carbethoxy furo(5,4':6,7)coumarin but on hydrolysis it gave a non-melting product.

A number of furocoumarins of different types have been synthesised so far but the furo-coumarin of the type (Ia) has been known only in the form of its derivatives. Thus 4-methyl-5-n-propylfuro(5',4':6,7) coumarin (Ib) and 2',4-dimethylfuro(5',4':6,7) coumarin (Ic) have been

7-formyl- or 6-hydroxy-7-allylcoumarin are not easily accessible as the substitution in 6-hydroxycoumarin usually takes place in the 5-position.

We have now tried a new approach to the synthesis of the furocoumarins of the type (Ia). 7-Formyl-4-methylcoumarin was obtained from 7-bromomethyl-4-methylcoumarin² by heating with hexamine. This was subjected to Elbs-persulphate oxidation when 6-hydroxy-7-formyl-4-methylcoumarin (IIa) was obtained. That the Elbs I persulphate oxidation in coumarin derivatives takes place in the 6-position when that position is free has been shown conclusively in numerous cases³. On condensation with ethyl bromoacetate, it gave the 6-carbethoxymethoxy derivative (IIIa). Thus was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid which on cyclisation gave 2'-carboxy-4-methylfuro(5',4':6,7) coumarin. On decarboxylation it gave the furocoumarin (Id). We next tried to synthesise the parent compound (Ia) by using this route. 7-Bromomethylcoumarin was prepared from 7-methylcoumarin by reacting it with N-bromo-succinimide in the presence of benzoyl peroxide. This was converted into 7-formylcoumarin by heating with hexamine. On Elbs-persulphate oxidation it gave 6-hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin (IIb). This on condensation with ethylbromoacetate gave the 6-carbethoxymethoxy derivative (IIIb) but its hydrolysis did not give the desired acid, instead a non-melting polymeric product was obtained. 6-Hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin was therefore condensed with ethyl-bromomalonate to synthesise the furocoumarin according to the method of Tanaka⁴. A product insoluble in alkali was obtained which analysed for 2'-carbethoxy-furo(5',4':6,7) coumarin but its hydrolysis and decarboxylation met with failure. Hydrolysis with sodium hydroxide gave a non-melting polymeric product. With conc. sulphuric acid in the cold no hydrolysis took place.

- Ia. $R=R'=R''=H$
 b. $R=CH_3; R'=n-C_3H_7; R''=H$
 c. $R=CH_3; R'=H; R''=CH_3$
 d. $R=CH_3; R'=R''=H$

- IIa. $R=CH_3$
 b. $R=H$

- IIIa. $R=CH_3$
 b. $R=H$

synthesised¹. The parent furocoumarin (Ia) has not yet been synthesised, probably because the intermediates required for its synthesis such as 6-hydroxy-

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Experimental†

4-Methyl-7-formylcoumarin : 4-Methyl-7-bromomethylcoumarin² (1 g.) was refluxed with hexamine (2.5 g.) in acetic acid (25 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Hydrochloric acid (10 ml.; 1 : 1) was then added and the heating continued for further 10 min. The product obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 201°. (Found : C, 70.38; H, 4.34. $C_{11}H_8O_3$ requires C, 70.21; H, 4.24%.)

The 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone : Prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene in orange yellow needles, m.p. > 300°. (Found : N, 15.17; $C_{17}H_{12}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.22%.)

6-Hydroxy-4-methyl-7-formylcoumarin : 4-Methyl-7-formylcoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (15 ml.; 10%) by warming and saturated potassium persulphate (1.6 g.) solution was added during 4 hr with continuous stirring and external cooling. The solution was kept overnight and then acidified to congo red. The precipitated unreacted substance was removed by filtration and the filtrate was heated with excess of hydrochloric acid on a steam bath for 30 min. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 287°. It gave a reddish brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 64.54; H, 3.60. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires C, 64.71; H, 3.92%.)

6-Carboethoxymethoxy-4-methyl-7-formylcoumarin : The above coumarin (1.5 g.) in dry acetone was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (3 ml.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) till the solution became colourless. Acetone was then removed and the residue was treated with excess of water. The product obtained crystallised from benzene in white needles (0.75 g.), m.p. 173°. (Found : C, 62.19; H, 4.97. $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 62.07; H, 4.82%.)

6-Carboxymethoxy-4-methyl-7-formylcoumarin : The above ester (0.5 g.) was kept with sodium hydroxide solution for 24 hr. when a clear solution was obtained. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid in white tiny needles (0.39 g.), m.p. 237°. (Found : C, 59.4; H, 4.06. $C_{13}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 59.54; H, 3.81%.)

2'-Carboxy-4-methylfuro(5', 4' : 6, 7) coumarin : The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hr. on a wire gauze. The solid separating on adding the reaction mixture to water crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. > 300°. Yield 0.3 g. The product was soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution. (Found : C, 63.98; H, 3.23. $C_{13}H_8O_5$ requires C, 63.93; H, 3.28%.)

4-Methylfuro(5', 4' : 6, 7) coumarin : The above acid (0.45 g.) was refluxed with quinoline (5 ml.) and

copper bronze (1 g.) for 1 hr. The solution was filtered and the filtrate added to ice cold hydrochloric acid. The separating product crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow wooly needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 186°. (Found : C, 72.33; H, 4.08. $C_{12}H_8O_3$ requires C, 72.00; H, 4.00%.)

7-Bromomethylcoumarin : 7-Methylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with N-bromosuccinimide (1 g.) and benzoyl peroxide (0.01 g.) in dry benzene on a steam bath for 6 hr. The solvent was removed and the product washed with hot water and crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 182°. (Found : Br, 33.45; $C_{10}H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 33.47%.)

7-Formylcoumarin : 7-Bromomethylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with hexamine (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Hydrochloric acid (1 : 1; 10 ml.) was then added and the heating continued for further 10 mins. The product obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 205°. (Found : C, 68.93; H, 3.62. $C_{10}H_6O_3$ requires C, 68.98; H, 3.44%.)

The 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone : Prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow needles, m.p. > 300°. (Found : N, 15.63. $C_{16}H_{10}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.82%.)

6-Hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin : 7-Formylcoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in warm sodium hydroxide solution and potassium persulphate (0.6 g.) added during 4 hr. with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and worked up as before. The compound obtained crystallised from nitrobenzene in pale yellow prisms (0.25 g.), m.p. 268°. It gave a reddish brown colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 62.94; H, 2.75. $C_{10}H_6O_4$ requires C, 63.16; H, 3.15%.)

6-Carboethoxymethoxy-7-formylcoumarin : 6-Hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin (1 g.) was refluxed with ethylbromoacetate (3 ml.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) till the solution became colourless. The product obtained on working up as before crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in white needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 128°. (Found : C, 60.91; H, 4.66. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 60.87; H, 4.34%.)

Attempt to hydrolyse with alkali to a non-melting polymeric product.

2'-Carboethoxyfuro(5', 4' : 6, 7) coumarin : 6-Hydroxy-7-formylcoumarin (1 g.) in ethyl methylketone (50 ml.) was refluxed for 5 hr. with ethyl bromomalonate (0.56 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.). The product obtained on removal of the solvent and addition of water crystallised from acetic acid in pale yellow needles (0.55 g.), m.p. 238°. (Found : C, 65.39; H, 3.89. $C_{14}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 65.12; H, 3.87%.)

† All the melting points are uncorrected.

On heating with alkali it gave a non-melting polymeric product.

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